

Table 3. Distribution and prevalence of races of *P. oryzae* in Argentina.

Region	Races
Entre Rios:	
Concepcion del Uruguay	IA ₂ , Unidentified
Villaguay	II ₁
Chaco	IB ₁₀ and ID ₁₁
Formosa	IA ₆ and IB ₉
Santa Fe	IA ₁₂₆
Buenos Aires:	
La Plata	IA ₃₈ and IA ₉
Unknown	IF ₃

new group, II, characterized by a resistant reaction on all eight IRBD varieties. No isolates of IC, IE, IG, or IH were detected. Isolate G4-78 was not identified. The most prevalent race group was IA (40%) followed by IB (16%), II₁ (16%), and ID and IF (8%). The four commercial varieties were susceptible to most races (Table 2). The geographical distribution of races is shown in Table 3. The prevalent races in Argentina are similar to those in Colombia as reported by Galvez in 1971. No correlation between colony type and pathogenicity was obtained. ■

Correlation of rice varietal reaction to brown spot disease and postinfectious production of fungitoxic substance

D. N. Giri, and A. K. Sinha, Plant Pathology Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani 741235, West Bengal, India

There is good evidence that rice plants produce phytoalexin-like fungitoxic substances. A basic postulate of the phytoalexin concept is that host varieties differ in speed of phytoalexin production when infected; resistant varieties produce more than susceptible varieties. Our two experiments on brown spot disease of rice provide some relevant information.

Pot-grown, 3-week-old plants representing 9 varieties were artificially inoculated with a virulent isolate of *Helminthosporium oryzae*; symptoms were assessed 4 days later to compute a disease index on the basis of both the number and size of lesions. Diffusates

Reactions of rice cultivars to infection with *H. oryzae* and fungitoxicity in diffusates from infected plants. West Bengal, India.

Cultivar	Experiment 1			Experiment 2		
	Mean lesion size, length x breadth (mm)	Mean disease index/plant	Inhibition (%) of germ tube growth ^a	Mean no. of spots/plant	Mean disease index/plant	Inhibition (%) of germ tube growth ^a
Benibhog	2.61 x 0.51	10.4	6.2	41.7	11.9	8.3
Dharial	2.13 x 0.58	9.4	21.2	37.5	10.4	25.2
Dular	2.15 x 0.40	1.2	25.4			
Badkalam				40.4	9.6	34.1
IR8				36.8	8.2	35.9
Padma				34.6	5.2	41.5
Lathisail	2.10 x 0.32	4.1	55.4			
AC1351				41.4	4.8	70.0
CH13	1.83 x 0.25	3.5	65.9	34.5	3.6	71.8

^a Values indicate percentage reduction in germ tube growth in the diffusate from inoculated plants in terms of that in the diffusate from uninoculated plants.

from the leaves of both uninoculated and inoculated plants (collected 3 days after inoculation) were assayed for toxic action against spore germination of the pathogen.

The general trend in both experiments was the same (see table). The diffusate from inoculated Benibhog plants, which had the highest mean disease index and lesions of largest mean size, exhibited the least fungitoxicity. CH13 plants had the lowest disease index and the smallest mean size of lesions. The CH13 leaf diffusate showed the highest fungitoxicity. Other varieties between these two extremes showed an inverse correlation between disease index and fungitoxicity

in leaf diffusate, but the differences between different varieties were not always proportional. Varieties differed little in number of lesions, although they differed in mean lesion size. Resistant varieties generally developed more of the smaller spots and fewer of the larger spots than the susceptible ones. It is apparent that the production of fungitoxic substance is more rapid in incompatible than in compatible host-parasite interactions. This may explain the occurrence of more of the smaller-sized spots in the former. Observations are in agreement with the phytoalexin concept. ■

Sources of resistance to major rice diseases in the Punjab, India

G. L. Raina, Gurjit Singh, and G. S. Sidhu, Punjab Agricultural University, Rice Research Station, Kapurthala, Punjab, India

In 1979 kharif we screened 282 of our breeding lines for resistance to bacterial blight, sheath blight, sheath rot, and stem rot. Ten plants of each line were artificially inoculated with pure cultures of the pathogens of those diseases separately. Plants were inoculated at maximum tillering for bacterial blight, at booting for sheath blight and sheath rot, and at heading for stem rot. Inoculation methods were clipping for bacterial blight; Amin's stem tape-inoculation technique for sheath blight;

inserting pearl millet grain culture inside the flag leaf sheath, just above the floret, for sheath rot; and injecting sclerotial suspension into the base of the stem at water level for stem rot. Disease reactions were recorded 15 days after inoculation for bacterial blight, 20 days for sheath blight and sheath rot, and 30 days for stem rot. The Standard Evaluation System scale was used for bacterial blight and sheath blight evaluation. For sheath rot, a 1-9 scale suggested by Satyanarayana and Reddy (IRRN 4 [Apr 1979] 6) was used. For stem rot the following scale was designed:

R = resistant (Sclerotia not formed)
 MR = moderately resistant (Few sclerotia visible inside the stem)
 M = intermediate (Many to abundant sclerotia visible inside the stem)